

METHODS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION USING ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AND VR TECHNOLOGY

Kojabekova Gulbadam Kudaynazarovna

*2nd year student of master's degree of Information technologies in education,
Nukus State Pedagogical Institute*

Daniyarova Ulbosin Kuatbaevna

*2nd year student of master's degree of Information technologies in education,
Nukus State Pedagogical Institute*

Abstract: *In this article, we describe some of the methods and technologies used to improve the quality of education. Nowadays, technologies are rapidly developing with the demand of time and the new concept of VR has entered the field of education and has become an integral part of our life. It is very important and significant to improve the quality of education using electronic resources in the methodology.*

Key words: *educational resources, VR technology, quality of education, e-class, artificial reality, digital technologies.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7792001>

INTRODUCTION: The need to transition to the information society is a new technology in the world economy order formation and priority, socio-economic information resources transition to real resources of development, information products and society meeting the demand for services, information in the social development system increasing importance of communication infrastructure, international information exchanges on the basis of improvement of educational, scientific, technical and cultural spheres, "global information benefits" are conditioned by using them on the basis of equal rights. Electronic in recent years advantages of education compared to traditional education are being identified more. In recent times, learners and teachers are part of traditional education to the conclusion that the advantages of online education are more than those of other types they are coming. The reason is digital, aimed at improving the quality of education in the education system educational platforms are increasing, in which traditional and online education are the most mixed education system is being formed by combining the good aspects. Mixed education low price, flexibility, free of charge, besides, in the educational process the advantage of using complex technologies is the reason for this alternative. Interest in this trend affects students in the educational process and education increases the quality. Many studies have shown that online learning promotes creative thinking in students showed that it is the cause of development, that is, independent education of students adaptation to the educational process, taking into account individual needs is the basis for forming the ability.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION: Teaching in the real time system through the Internet in the current era of globalization is considered one of the rapidly developing types of education. The e-learning system provides education and training at a voluntary distance without any

barriers makes it possible to get Experts say that traditional education teaching in a real-time distance education system compared to the system efficiency is higher (Means, Toyama, Murphy, Bakiya, & Jones, 2013). Real use of video lectures in the distance education system in the time system is the most is an effective teaching method. For example, Wang (2008) in Taiwan 10 years of studying in the field of medicine, a video on medicine taught online. He says that with the help of lectures, the medical service among the population has improved. Again one example is Chung-Eng, located in Seoul, the capital of South Korea. The university has an online electronic class (e-class) for each subject. To science a student who has registered for participation will also have the right to enter the —e-class. In this —e-class, presentations are made not only in Microsoft Power Point but there are also video lectures and homework assignments. Training is known a student who could not attend the lesson or did not master the lesson well —e-class can access video lectures. This is definitely an education that it will further increase its efficiency and provide a basis for the training of mature personnel. Currently, information and communication technologies are used in the educational process (ICT) is increasing its effectiveness in education remains one of the most favorable factors. That is why advanced countries computer technology, modern information communication in the educational system research aimed at effective use of technologies is non-stop is passing. In general, today's society is standard industrialized transition from economy to new economy is being observed. Customers of the new economy - is the economy of users, so the world information. The main factor in the development of the telecommunications industry is the new generation providing services.

Basic mechanisms of integration of science and production in education development, implementation, study, independent distance education system individualization of learning, development and mastering of technology, using ET on the basis of new pedagogical and information technologies. Acceleration of students' education is one of such urgent tasks. Education organization of the process on the basis of ET, including the description of educational materials, it will be necessary to make certain changes to the principles of improvement. In this introduction of modern information technologies to the educational process and from them use is the most effective way to achieve the goal.

The use of ET is the skill of users in communicating with them and skills. Therefore, at first, modern telecommunications, it is important to know what the means are. The capabilities of modern telecommunications are a very wide system, computer, multimedia tools, computer networks known to him, in addition to concepts such as the Internet, a number of new concepts are included. To these information systems, information systems management, information transmission systems, database, database management system, knowledge repository can be an example. To the field of education in the 21st century information age introduction of electronic education in every educational institution: teaching and learning process; management of the educational institution; activity of the educational institution environment requires information. Organization of ET environment in the educational institution, the stages of achievement begin with the creation of a psychological information environment. Technological and modern tools based on scientific results, created software products and the need to use methods is formed. This is in every educational institution independent and computer pedagogues on the basis of

individual and advisory training, it is necessary to organize an education system. Organization of information resources in the field of education and use in education is paid special attention in our country, education introduction of ET into the system, first of all, to the intellectual potential of society, including the informatization of the education sector, the development of information and educational resources depending on the output. The integration of education with science and production is justified development of mechanisms, its implementation, learning, independent knowledge individualization of learning, distance education (MT) system technology and development and mastering of tools, new pedagogy and information acceleration of students' studies using ET based on technologies is among such important tasks. Organize the educational process on the basis of ET including the principles of improving the presentation of educational materials. It will be necessary to make certain changes. ICT in the educational process (in particular, MT process) is mainly used in two ways. The first condition is this in the case of technical equipment, and the second condition is with special software provided.

Virtual reality (VR, English: virtual reality, VR, artificial reality) is a world created by technical means, transmitted to a person through his senses: sight, hearing, touch, etc. Virtual reality simulates both impact and reaction. Perform computer synthesis of virtual reality and real-time reactions for a robust set of reality experiences. The power of virtual objects is kept close to the security of an object resembling the reality of physical reality. real laws of physics (gravity, properties of water, collisions with objects, reflections, etc.) can effectively help these objects. However, users of virtual worlds are often given more permission than in real life for recreational purposes (such as flying, searching for certain items, etc.). Virtual reality should not be confused with real reality. The main difference between them is that virtual reality builds a new artificial world, while augmented reality only adds certain artificial objects to the perception of the real world. Modern virtual glasses (English: HMD-display) are not helmets, but glasses, and contain one or more displays that display images for the left and right eyes, a lens system for correcting the image geometry, and a tracking system that monitors the orientation of the device in space. Typically, virtual reality helmet loading systems are based on gyroscopes, accelerometers, and magnetometers. For such systems, wide field of view, accuracy in tracking the tilt and turn of the user's head, determining the position of the head in space and displaying a clear image are moderately minimal. It includes many different devices, from some smartphones to virtual reality rooms (CAVEs). The three embedded devices give the user the illusion of a three-dimensional object by displaying specially shaped projections on one or more virtual displays based on information about the user's eye position. the effective eye positions depicted in the displays themselves, and the corresponding changes in them. It also provides a stereo image for stereoscopic stereo displays. Various additional optical technologies are used for this: (detecting the coordinates of the user's eyes in the image from the camera, saving active or passive markers), small - ultrasound. Often, tracking systems can include additional devices: gyroscopes, accelerometers and magnetometers. For remote systems, the accuracy of the user's position in space, the specificity of the position of the head in space, and the minimum delay in displaying the corresponding image are important. Here, systems can be implemented in different shapes and sizes: from direct immersion in a virtual

room to virtual reality on a three-inch virtual screen. Office equipment creates an image directly on the retina, the user sees an image "Hanging" in the air in front of them. Operating devices are directly close to real systems because the virtual objects that the user sees are images of real objects. The implementation is possible under certain conditions (dark room, retinal coating and connection with tracking system) to immerse the user in virtual reality on these devices. Various hybrid options are also possible: for example, getting the correct projection of the image onto the plane is achieved by viewing the projectors directly, and the stereoscopic output reflection on the surface helps, made the projection. But so far, such products are not widely used and are produced only in the form of prototypes. Such a system is a room that projects a 3D stereo image onto all walls. The user's position and head rotation are controlled by tracking systems, which ensures maximum immersion efficiency. These systems are actively used for marketing, military, scientific and other purposes. The person described above is influenced by their emotions, but information can be transmitted directly to the nerve endings and even directly to the brain through brain interfaces. A similar technology is used in medicine to replace lost sensory abilities, but so far it is too expensive for everyday use and does not achieve the quality of data transmission acceptable for virtual reality transmission. Various physiotherapeutic devices and devices are based on the same principle and reproduce real-world sensations in an altered state of consciousness ("Radoson", etc.).

The main task of education is to form the skills that the student will need today and in the future to lead a successful life in society. Creative thinking is an important skill for today's youth (Lucas and Spencer, 2017 [15]). These skills help them adapt to a world that is constantly and rapidly changing, requiring workers with "21st century" skills that go beyond simple literacy. In general, today's student is expected to work in areas that do not even exist now, to solve new problems using new technologies. Formation of creative thinking skills in students allows them to solve increasingly complex local and global problems through an unusual approach, digital technologies- Internet of Things (IoT). To digital information, one of the key technologies based on this is the Internet of things. Many household appliances, It's common to be plugged in, but gradually more and more of the physical world, objects are connected to the Internet, which allows to collect information and even control these objects remotely allows to control. Indeed, on the Internet, the object and the outside world are different which includes parameters and allows the object via the Internet, a virtual copy of the physical object appears. An example of the Internet of Things is in the cinema a device such as a projector from a detected fault and plan to the technical support service a signal about the list of spare parts to be replaced as part of the external repair sends.

CONCLUSION: Digital technologies - virtual reality (Virtual reality, VR). Human in virtual reality the appearance of technical devices that allow this technology made it in demand in the entertainment industry. Virtual reality helmets and suits, specialized rooms allow you to enter an unknown world, which is all your actions are programmed to respond from the virtual world, giving you totally allows you to immerse yourself.

REFERENCES:

1. Jasur Doniyor o'g'li Saidov, Saydullo Payzievich Allayorov, Said Xalilovich Islikov, Ma'lumotlar omborini yaratish bo'yicha kasbiy kompetentligini baholash mezonlari // Scientific progress. 2021. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ma-lumotlaromborini-yaratish-bo-yicha-kasbiy-kompetentligini-baholash-mezonlari> (дата обращения: 02.06.2022).
2. Toshtemirov D., Muminov B., Saidov J. Fundamentals of compilation of electronic tasks for students to test and strengthen their knowledge of database //International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research. – 2020. – Т. 9, – №. 4. –С. 3226-3228.
3. Грегг Б. «Производительность систем: Enterprise и Cloud», 2014. https://koptelov.info/publikatsii/digital_technology.
4. Bakiyeva, F. R., Primkulova, A. A., & Mirzahmedova, N. D. (2020). Smart And Development Of Modern Education.